

HOW NOVEL TECHNOLOGIES CAN CONTRIBUTE TO REDUCE MACROPLASTIC AND MICROPLASTIC LITTER RELEASED INTO THE MARINE ENVIRONMENT? THE TECHNOLOGIES OF THE CLAIM PROJECT

SUMMARY

The Horizon 2020 Innovation Action “**C**leaning **L**itter by developing and **A**pplying **I**nnovative **M**ethods in European seas” (**CLAIM**) is a 4.5 years' project that brought together 21 partners from 13 European Union countries, Tunisia and Lebanon and received funding from the EU under Grant Agreement No 774586. CLAIM focused on the development of five innovative cleaning technologies, modelling tools and approaches fostering ecosystem services, targeting the prevention and *in situ* management of visible (macroplastics >5 mm) and invisible (micro <5 mm) marine litter at their point of introduction to the marine environment (river estuaries and wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs)), towards the mitigation and efficient ecosystem management of marine litter pollution in the Mediterranean and Baltic Seas.

The project developed four innovative cleaning technologies and approaches, targeting the prevention of macro and microplastic at their point of introduction to the marine environment, as well as the plastic pollution management in the Mediterranean and Baltic Seas. To prevent the spread of marine litter, CLAIM researchers suggest the urgent implementation of several comprehensive methods and technologies. The project partners have successfully designed and tested four CLAIM technologies, namely:

- 1) a low-cost, automated and self-cleaning **filtering system for microplastics for WWTPs**, the **Waste & Water EcoPlex Microplastic Remover**[®];
- 2) a **photocatalytic nanocoating device (Photocatalytic Reactor)**, which is used for speeding up sun-fueled degradation and breaking down microplastics into harmless elements;
- 3) an **innovative floating boom (floating barrier- CLEAN TRASH[®] system¹)** which collects and sustains litter and macroplastics at river mouths;
- 4) a **small-scale thermal treatment device (PYROLYSER)** that transforms solid marine litter into a combustible gas, called syngas.

KEYWORDS

Plastic pollution, macroplastics, microplastics, cleaning marine plastic technologies, marine biodiversity, marine ecosystems, Mediterranean and Baltic seas

1 **CLAIM's Litter Entrapping Autonomous Network Tactical Recovery Accumulation System Hellas**

RELEVANCE TO LEGISLATION

- Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) (2008/56/EC)
- Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC)
- European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy (COM/2018/028)
- Port Reception Facilities (PRF) Directive (2019/883/EU)
- Urban Wastewater Treatment (UWWT) Directive (91/271/EEC) and its ongoing revision²
- Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC)
- Marine Equipment Directive (2014/90/EU)
- Directive on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment (Single Use Plastics (SUP) Directive 2019/904/EU)
- HELCOM's Regional Action Plan for Marine Litter in the Baltic Sea
- OSPAR's Regional Action Plan for Prevention and Management of Marine Litter in the North-East Atlantic
- UNEP/MAP's Regional Plan on Marine Litter Management in the Mediterranean
- Basel Convention's Plastic Waste Amendments
- MARPOL Convention's Annex V

RELEVANCE TO ACTUAL ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS

Biodiversity, marine pollution, human well-being

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² See: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/12405-Water-pollution-EUrules-on-urban-wastewater-treatment-update-/public-consultation_en

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DESCRIPTION OF THE PROBLEM

The Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) states that “marine environment is a precious heritage that must be protected, preserved and, where practicable, restored with the ultimate aim of maintaining biodiversity and providing diverse and dynamic oceans and seas which are clean, healthy and productive”. The Directive promotes the sustainable and efficient protection of the marine environment. In accordance with the MSFD, CLAIM develops and demonstrates innovative technologies and approaches, suitable for removing micro and macroplastic litter at their point of introduction to the marine environment, as well as already located in the marine environment. The primary objective of CLAIM is to provide practical tools for a step change towards the mitigation and efficient ecosystem management of marine litter pollution in the Mediterranean Sea and Baltic Sea.

CLAIM'S TECHNOLOGIES:

Waste & Water EcoPlex Microplastic Remover®

For the wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs), a series of prototypes developed, including an up-scaled prototype that uses a synthesis of filter media that contain material for solids retention. This pre-filtering system was further up-scaled by Waste and Water (WnW) resulting to a low-cost, automated and self-cleaning **filtering system for microplastics for WWTPs**, the **Waste & Water EcoPlex Microplastic Remover®**, that has been designed and fabricated at a TRL8. The CLAIM prototype can treat water volumes of 30 m³/day but it is scalable and can treat the whole volume of a WWTP that is discharged into the sea. Its main purpose is to retain microplastics up to 50µm and to adapt its mechanical characteristics to the specifications of the effluent taken from the WWTP outlet and the requirements of the photocatalytic nanocoating device (see below). It has a TRL of 8 and an average efficiency of microplastics retention of 99.04%.

Figure 1. The Waste & Water EcoPlex Microplastic Remover®

Figure 2. The photocatalytic reactor of KTH and DEVENTUS.

Photocatalytic nanocoating device (Photocatalytic Reactor)

The retained microplastics in the **EcoPlex** device are fed into a **photocatalytic nanocoating device (Photocatalytic Reactor)** composed by a photocatalytic oxide, grown on a suitable substrate, designed and constructed by KTH and DEVENTUS in Sweden. Using green nanotechnology-based coatings that enhance polymer degradation, i.e metal oxide semiconductor nanostructures chemically attached to supporting membranes, the device ensures photochemical activity without releasing the nanoparticles into the water-stream. The photocatalytic metaloxide upon excitation with sunlight generate active radicals that attack the polymeric chains breaking them down in simple innocuous compounds, hence effectively dissolving the plastics. A prototype was up-scaled to 1x1 m panel by the company DEVENTUS. The **Photocatalytic Reactor** has a TRL of 6 and show a trapping efficiency of 82%.

Innovative floating boom (floating barrier- CLEAN TRASH® system)

The **CLEAN TRASH® system** retains, collects and monitors floating litter (that include macroplastics) and is specifically devised to operate in river mouths and waterways that reached a TRL 9. This highly-efficient solution manages to collect and sustain litter and macroplastics at river mouths before entering into the open sea and affecting the marine ecosystem. The scale model was built at New Naval's facility in Lavrio, Greece, in late 2018 and a prototype was deployed at the river mouth of Kifissos river in Athens, Greece in 2019, where it was possible to estimate that the system may capture about 95-97% of macrolitter (> 5 mm). The effectiveness and capabilities of the system passed all quality assurance testing, confirming that the system is ready to be installed in active, long-term operational environments. It can continuously contain and remove marine litter from river mouths and be a commercial product purchased by authorities and all stakeholders related to marine litter pollution.

Figure 3. The CLEAN TRASH® system of NNL

SMALL SCALE PYROLYSER

The collected marine litter from the **CLEAN TRASH®** system can be treated in an **innovative small-scale thermal treatment device (PYROLYSER)**. Pyrolysis is a tertiary recycling process of macro plastic non-recyclable materials (marine litter in CLAIM project) in the absence of oxidants (oxygen, air, water) with conversion of the same into high quality Syngas (CO , CH_4 , hydrogen, light hydrocarbons) by thermal decomposition in the absence or presence of catalysts. It is an endothermic process at temperatures range from 300°C to 900°C . The optimal temperatures are between 500°C and 700°C . The traditional thermal pyrogasification processes have some disadvantages due to temperatures relatively low, as yields in syngas are not excellent and the formation of oils / tars which cannot be completely avoided. These problems are largely due to relatively low heating. The use of thermal plasma (PYR1) and thermal induction (PYR2) allows to reach speeds of heating and much higher temperatures, resulting in increased product yields of pyrolysis. The devices developed in CLAIM use external heat (assisted pyrolysis) as a physical element for marine litter treatment, which is why it is called a small-scale assisted PYROLYSER for thermal treatment of marine litter and waste technology.

To reach the project goal and requirements, focusing on *in situ* cleaning, two devices were designed, built, and tested by IRIS srl: each one oriented to a specific operational context. The devices are small-scale and use external heat (assisted pyrolysis) as a physical element

for marine litter treatment, which is why it is called a small-scale assisted PYROLYSER for thermal treatment of marine litter and waste technology. The system aims at being the turning point; it is a system capable of converting marine litter, mainly present in coastal areas and ports, into 100% renewable energy with high efficiency, low emissions, low costs. Both assisted pyrolysis PYR1 and PYR2 devices are an innovative evolution of the Plasma PYROLYSER (EP3023693), developed and owned by IRIS.

PYR1: The plasma-assisted pyrolysis device designed and built by IRIS to work in port areas connected to the public electricity grid. The system is fully contained in a 20' container (Fig.4). The device consists of a plasma-assisted reactor, which under high temperatures and isolated conditions allows a pyrolysis reaction. The absence of oxygen in turn allows a dioxin-free reaction. Other unwanted compounds are filtered out and treated with reagents at high temperatures, resulting in a clean and energy-rich syngas.

PYR2: The induction-assisted pyrolysis device designed and built by IRIS oriented to work on boats and vessels coupled with Lithium battery which allow to be the system completely self-sufficient: capable to carry out marine cleaning campaigns without external energy. The system is fully contained in a 10' container and plug-and play (Fig.5). The PYR2 produces syngas, which can be re-used on fuel ships and heat ports as well. The process does not produce dioxins and furans, an issue with many thermal processes.

Figure 4. Illustration of the PYR1 of IRIS on port installation

Figure 5. Illustration of the PYR2 on board on an electric vessel

The syngas produced by the PYR1 and PYR2, after the cleaning operations (elimination of pollutants, condensates, and filtration) is fed into an internal combustion engine able to produce an electric energy and thermal energy.

The electricity produced by the system (PYR1 and PYR2) is greater than that consumed even if of a reduced quantity. The electrical balance (electrical energy produced is more than the electrical energy consumed) is positive in both devices: 100 kg of marine waste per day allow to obtain 220 Nm³ (PYR2) or 250 Nm³ (PYR1) of syngas with a total calorific value of 205 kWh and a net total electricity production of 18 kWh (PYR1) and 22 kWh (PYR2)³.

Their TRL level is 7. CLAIM's pyrolysers are capable of handling up to 100 kg of waste per day (5kg/h) with a positive electric energy balance. Each kg of marine litter makes it possible to obtain 2,5 Nm³/h of syngas, with a calorific value of 2,05 kilowatt-hours (kWh) and a net production of unitary electricity of 0,2 kWh. By increasing the treated marine litter to 30-70 kg/h, using assisted-pyrolysis induction technology combined with catalysts for the treatment of syngas, it will be possible to achieve a significant increase in generated electricity and a clear reduction in OPEX, making the device attractive to the market.

³ With 1 kWh power we may iron (1,000 watts) for 60 minutes or cook in an oven (2,000 watts) for 30 minutes, or use a laptop (20-50 watts) all day, or keep a broadband router (7-10 watts) on for five days or watch a 42" LED TV (80 watts) for 12 and a half hours.

Figure 6. 3D representation of the system without coating panels and with protective coating panels

Figure 7. PYR1 in operational position in the port of Genova.

Figure 8. PYR2 on board

ECOLOGICAL IMPACT:

There are currently several technologies adopted for the treatment of non-differentiable waste, in specific:

- Incineration/combustion: widespread.
- Gasification: not very widespread, used for organic waste or biomass.
- Pyrolysis: not very widespread, used for organic waste or biomass.

The great potential of the PYR system is to have small dimensions, to be transportable and therefore used for the on-site treatment of small quantities of waste, eliminating the costs and emissions of transporting waste to the treatment plant.

In PYR1 and PYR2, the viscous residue that consists of larger hydrocarbon chains, normally can be reinserted the PYROLYSER chamber reactor to increase the calorific value of syngas; the residue found in the reaction chamber is vitrified residue which can therefore be used as a material for road maintenance operations together with asphalt. In the Pyrolysis process, the marine litter/waste is not a fuel, but a feedstock for a high temperature chemical conversion process. In fact, pyrolysis allows the production of a syngas that can feed an internal combustion engine (CLAIM device) a Fuel cell (future evolution) and thus obtain cogeneration (electricity + thermal energy). The internal combustion engine during the conversion of syngas into electrical energy produces fumes (about 7 Nm³/h per kg of waste) that broadly comply with the emission limits of the law. The engine is in fact a commercial system equipped with a particulate filter and a NOX catalyst. There is no unburnt gas (CO) in the exhaust fumes. The fumes are mainly composed of water vapor, nitrogen and carbon dioxide (<10% in volume).

For every kWh of electric energy produced by PYR system (started from marine litter collected) is produced 0,837 kgCO₂/kWh compared to 1,376 kgCO₂/kWh produced with a traditional waste-to-energy system^{4,5}.

4 Standard CO2 emission factors (from IPCC, 2006) and CO2-equivalent LCA emission factors (from ELCD) for most common fuel types

5 Eriksson, Ola & Finnveden, Göran. (2009). Plastic waste as a fuel – CO2-neutral or not? Energy & Environmental Science. 2. 907-914. 10.1039/b908135f.

CONCLUSIONS

Innovative environmental technologies can play a crucial role in solving marine plastic pollution. Together with other measures like policy improvements, change in consumer behaviour, partnerships between different players (e.g. technology developers and vendors) and coordination of decisions between EU, national and local authorities, will make it possible to build overall sustainable solutions. The CLAIM project developed technologies and modelling tools that have a proven effect in the reduction of marine plastic pollution in European Seas and can be directly used in other Continents as well.

MODELLING TOOLS ASSIST GOVERNANCE TO REDUCE PLASTIC POLLUTION

In the CLAIM project, a series of model scenario simulations were performed in the Mediterranean and Baltic Seas, in order to **assess the utility of CLAIM cleaning technologies** in reducing the impact of plastic pollution on sensitive ecosystem services. Micro- and macroplastics distributions were simulated assuming a fixed (25%, 50%, 75%) representing pragmatic estimates of cleaning success in WWTPs and River source inputs. These were overlapped with areas of high ecological and commercial importance, such as Cetacean Critical Habitats, Natura 2000, aquaculture (shellfish, finfish) and recreational beaches, where the relative decrease of plastic pollution was assessed, following the adopted reduction on WWTPs and River source inputs. The estimates of the decrease in microplastic and macroplastic concentrations in the Baltic and Mediterranean Seas were very encouraging. In addition to the reduction estimates for the entire sea basins, the estimates are also given for selected ecosystem service layers. In the **Baltic Sea**, the results revealed that the reduction of inputs could cause a decrease in microplastics concentrations up to 50% (characteristic size of 5 µm), 62% (42 µm) and 68% (300 µm). Simulation of patterns of macroplastics distribution due to the input from a single source allows us to demonstrate the effects of the cleaning and related benefits if this particular source is removed. In turn, it could be used as advice for deciding where the cleaning has the highest impact and how far the impact is seen from the source. For example, the cleaning of the Oder river discharge has a considerable impact over a very large area in the southern Baltic Sea. Bathing sites with a potential decrease of the macroplastics concentrations of 50% or more are those close to the source (Oder river mouth), but also quite far, for instance at the coast of the Bornholm island.

For the **Mediterranean Sea**, for both small and large microplastics, the decrease of WWTP microplastics load (25%, 50%, 75%) results in a slightly lower (~85% of the load reduction, on average) mean concentration decrease (maximum 21%, 42%, 65%), progressively increasing as the load reduction is applied on an increasing number of sources (40, 120, 240, 400). For small macroplastics, the decrease of River macroplastics load (25%, 50%, 75%) results in a slightly lower (60-70% of the load reduction) mean concentration decrease (maximum 18%, 33%, 45%), progressively increasing as the load reduction is applied on an increasing number of sources (40, 120, 240, 400). For larger macroplastics, the decrease in the mean concentration is slightly smaller (~50-60% of the river load reduction). The theoretical contribution of such devices toward the reduction of plastic pollution has been tested in different areas in the Baltic and the Mediterranean Seas. For example, in the Saronikos Gulf area and the Natura conservation areas therein, was studied with the use of a 3-D coupled Hydrodynamic-Lagrangian litter tracking model. In all experiments performed, the installation of the CLAIM devices for a period of 2 years, resulted in a microplastics reduction by about 87% and a macroplastics reduction ranging from 13 to 43%, depending on the sources (Gkanasos et al., 2021, <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmars.2021.738876/full>).